

COSMETIC PURCHASE DECISION THROUGH MARKETING MIX DETERMINATION

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Abstract

Economic developments and people's lifestyles direct companies to be smart in attracting customers and maintaining and developing the market for cosmetic products. This research aims to determine the decision to purchase cosmetics by determining the marketing mix. This study was designed using qualitative and quantitative methods, with descriptive and verification approaches. Data collection techniques through observation, interviews, and distributing questionnaires that have been tested for validity and reliability to 200 samples taken by proportional random sampling technique. Methods of data analysis using multiple linear regression analysis, correlation coefficient analysis, analysis of the coefficient of determination, and hypothesis testing. The results of the research show that the marketing mix variables simultaneously or partially influence purchasing decisions. It is recommended that cosmetic product packaging should be made brighter and simpler, increase sales outlets and increase the diversity of information sources.

Keywords: Cosmetics, Marketing Mix, Purchasing Decision

INTRODUCTION

The development of people's purchasing power and lifestyle, which are getting smarter and looking for new things, encourages companies to develop marketing strategies to attract attention, maintain and control market share. Based on information from the Ministry of Home Affairs (2022), the total population of Indonesia is 273,879,750 people, with a composition of 138,303,472 people being male (50.5%) while the other 135,576,278 are female (49.5%). This data makes a potential market for the cosmetics industry because, with its high female population, Indonesia is a promising market share for the cosmetics business. Cosmetics are products that can meet women's basic needs for beauty (Abraham et al., 2022). Purchasing makeup products does not only fulfill wishes but is also a primary need for women, who are the main target of the cosmetic industry. This is evidenced by the many types of cosmetics that are produced domestically as well as foreign products.

Based on data, in January 2022, total sales of cosmetic products reached sales revenue of Rp. 34.3 billion, and in the following two months, it rose to 39%. The total sales of facial cosmetics as of March 2022 have earned sales revenue of up to IDR 129.1 billion (<https://compas.co.id/article/data-penjualan-kosmetik/>). This reflects a promising business opportunity for business people. Consequently, the level of competition between producers will also be increasingly sharp. An efficient and effective marketing strategy is needed to attract the attention of consumers to make purchasing decisions. The marketing strategy that can be done

is through the marketing mix. According to Aung (2020) in the concept of the marketing mix, there are marketing mix activities that can influence consumer decisions in buying cosmetic products, namely product, price,

LITERATURE REVIEW

Marketing is an important activity in a business because it affects business continuity during dynamic changes in the business environment. Business people are faced with conditions to always bring up creativity and innovation in packaging the marketing mix into an efficient and effective marketing strategy. The marketing strategy is part of a series of decisions regarding marketing tools which are often called the marketing mix. The marketing mix for cosmetic products is a series of marketing methods used by businesses/organizations to continue to achieve business goals in the target market (Dahiya & Gayatri, 2018; Hunt, 2018; Tong et al., 2020; Abraham et al., 2022). Amberg (2019); Britt et al. (2020); Tong et al. (2020); and Sharma (2021) explained that the marketing mix is often used in describing a combination of several inputs such as product, price, promotion, and distribution, which are the core of marketing activities. According to Aung (2020) and Faisal-E-Alam (2020), the concept of the marketing mix has continued to develop since it was first introduced by Borden (1965) and has been much refined with an understanding orientation to the combination of all that can be used as a marketing strategy, consisting of product, price, place, and promotion. The purchase decision made by a customer is considered a continuation of the action of selecting a product that he is interested in (Jaini et al., 2020; Khan et al., 2021; Wang et al., 2022). This is a consumer process of knowing the problem, looking for information about a particular product or brand, and evaluating how well each of these alternatives can solve the problem, which then leads to a purchase decision. Dahiya & Gayatri (2018) and Sharma (2021) suggest that the purchasing decision-making process has an identifiable path because the consumer decision flow, which includes determining whether a product or service is purchased or not to make a purchase is also a series of decisions obtained from previous activities, and will involve the certainty of buying or not. That is, a consumer who wants to choose must have choices to be used as a comparison in choosing something and purchasing decisions for products are closely related to consumer behavior (Ishak et al., 2020; Zhang & Dong, 2020; and Baharuddin et al., 2022).

METHOD

This study was designed using qualitative and quantitative methods, with descriptive and verification approaches. In this study, consumers who buy certain brands of cosmetics were determined as the population, and the determination of the sample in this study used a probability sampling technique with a purposive sampling procedure. The sample size was determined as many as 200 for subjective reasons (judgment) based on the theory, which states that an appropriate sample size in research is between 30 and 500, which is sufficient for most research (Roscoe in Echdar, 2017). Questionnaires on the results of validity and reliability tests were used to obtain primary data, which were then analyzed using multiple linear regression analysis, multiple correlations,

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The objects studied were 200 cosmetic consumers who purchased certain brand cosmetic products. Data obtained based on gender, age, last education, occupation, income, and type of cosmetic product purchased with the following description:

Table 1: Summary of Consumer Characteristics

No.	Characteristics	Criteria	Percentage (%)
1	Gender	Female	18
2	Age	18 – 30 years	60
3	Education	SMA/SMK equivalent	41
4	Occupation	Student	33
5	Income	Rp 1,000,000-Rp5,000,000	64
6	Products purchased by	Mascara	43

Based on Table 1, it can be seen that the majority of cosmetic consumers are women aged 18-30 years. The last level of education is SMA/SMK equivalent with a job as a student who has an income of IDR 1,000,000 to IDR 5,000,000 per month, with the dominant product purchased being mascara.

Recapitulation of consumer responses to the marketing mix and purchasing decisions is described in Table 2 and Table 3 below.

Table 2: Recapitulation of Consumer Responses to the Marketing Mix

No	Indicator	Value	Interpretation
Product			
1	Product Variety	4,68	Very varied, ranging from powder, lip gloss or lipstick, mascara, eyeliner, eyebrow pencil, blush to foundation
2	Product Quality	4,46	The selected cosmetics are very well-known and quality makeup brands with good makeup results, long-lasting and natural look
3	Brand Image	4,58	The selected cosmetics are very famous, with the number 1 makeup brand world with a good image
4	Product Packaging	4,19	Selected cosmetics are well-packaged and exclusive
	Average	4,47	The selected cosmetics are very well-known makeup brands with excellent images and quality, and the products are very varied and packaged exclusively.
Price			
1	Price affordability	3,38	The selected cosmetic makeup product prices are quite affordable
2	Price conformity with product quality	4,09	The price offered is suitable for all groups, accompanied by the appropriate product quality
3	Price competitiveness	3,84	The price offered for the selected cosmetic product can compete with other similar products
4	Price compatibility with benefits	4,43	The benefits of the selected cosmetic products are following the prices offered.
	Average	3,93	The quality and benefits obtained following the price offered are quite affordable for all people.
Location			

No	Indicator	Value	Interpretation
1	Place and strategic location	3,75	The selected cosmetic products are available at outlets in malls, shops, and minimarkets that are easy to reach
2	The security of the place to sell is maintained	4,32	Sales outlets are very safe and official to avoid product counterfeiting
3	Appearance of physical facilities is attractive	3,79	Products sold at outlets are arranged neatly and attractively
4	Product availability	3,34	Selected cosmetic products are sufficiently available through direct sales at outlets in malls, shops, and minimarkets, as well as online sales.
	Average	3,80	Selected cosmetic products are available in outlets in malls, shops, and minimarkets which are very safe with neat arrangements.
Promotion			
1	Information about products is easy to understand and informative	3,96	Information is conveyed by informative sales promotions so that consumers can immediately obtain the necessary information.
2	There are many sources of information available	3,32	Information about the selected cosmetics can be obtained through quite intense advertisements on television, in magazines, and on billboards
3	Product information encourages purchasing	3,83	Advertising on television, delivery of information through sales promotion, and sponsorship at events such as fashion encourages consumers to make purchases
4	Promotional messages delivered are easy to remember	4,47	The selected cosmetics are known through catchy catchphrases
	Average	3,89	Information on selected cosmetic products can be obtained through advertising, sales promotion, and sponsorship, which can encourage consumers to make purchases.

The recapitulation of consumer responses rated the selected cosmetic products very well. The product variety is the highest indicator, which is equal to 4.68, because the makeup products offered and selected vary according to the type of facial skin and the needs of its users, while product packaging is the lowest indicator, which is 4.19, which indicates that the product packaging for cosmetics is quite simple.

The majority of consumers consider the price of cosmetics to be reasonable and quite affordable. The price compatibility factor with the benefits obtained is the highest indicator, which is equal to 4.43. Consumers judge that the price of cosmetics is very suitable for its benefits, which reveal natural and long-lasting make-up.

The location factor is considered good by the majority of consumers, with the safety indicator of outlets being maintained being the highest score of 4.32. The product availability factor is the lowest indicator of 3.34 because currently, consumers can obtain cosmetic products through direct sales at outlets in malls, shops, minimarkets, and online sales.

The majority of consumers considered that the promotion was good and the promotional message delivered was easy to remember being the highest indicator, which was 4.47. This

cannot be separated from a slogan that is easy to recognize and remember. The factor of the number of available sources of information is the lowest indicator of 3.32 because consumers feel that promotional information about cosmetics on television, magazines, billboards, and other printed media is still relatively lacking.

Table 3: Recapitulation of Consumer Responses to Purchase Decisions

No.	Indicator	Value	Interpretation
1	Product choice	4.61	The choice of products is very diverse, ranging from powder, lip-gloss or lipstick, mascara, eyeliner, eyebrow pencil, blush to foundation
2	Choice of brands	4.14	Cosmetics is known as the world's number 1 makeup brand with good quality
3	Choice of dealers	3.31	Sales of cosmetic products are sufficiently available at certain outlets in malls, shops, and minimarkets
4	Purchase time	3.88	Consumers can buy products at any time, both offline through available outlets and online
5	Number of purchases	3.76	There are no special terms or conditions for purchasing, and there are no quantity restrictions for purchasing cosmetic products
6	Payment methods	3.95	Consumers can purchase products by paying cash, debit, or credit
Average		3.94	Consumers can buy a sufficient selection of cosmetic products available at outlets at any time without any special requirements.

Table 3 above explains that the majority of consumers value the decision to buy cosmetics well. The product choice factor is the highest indicator, which is equal to 4.61, with the assumption that consumers buy cosmetic products based on the various and widely available product choices on offer. The dealer selection factor is the lowest indicator of 3.31 because cosmetic products are only available at outlets in malls, shops, and minimarkets but are not yet available at outlets in traditional market areas.

The results of processing and analyzing the data using the multiple linear regression method obtained a regression equation with an estimated model as follows $Y = 13.236 + 0.030X_1 + 0.213X_2 + 0.248X_3 + 0.131X_4 + e$. Based on this equation, a positive constant value of 13.236 is obtained. The product regression coefficient (β_1) = 0.030 is also obtained, which indicates that the product factor has a positive effect on purchasing decisions. This means that if the product increases or is better, it is suspected that the purchase decision will also increase. The price regression coefficient (β_2) = 0.213 indicates that the price has a positive effect on purchasing decisions, meaning that if the price increases or is better, it is suspected that the purchasing decision will also increase.

Place or location factor (β_3) = 0.248, indicating that the place or location has a positive effect on purchasing decisions, meaning that if the place or location increases or is better, it is suspected that the purchasing decision will also increase. Promotion factor (β_4) = 0.131, indicating that promotion has a positive effect on purchasing decisions. This means that if the promotion increases or is better, it is assumed that the purchase decision will also increase.

Analysis of the correlation coefficient shows an r-value of 0.691, which is in the strong and positive category. This means that there is a strong and positive relationship between the

marketing mix and purchasing decisions. If there is an increase in the marketing mix, it will be followed by strengthening purchasing decisions. The coefficient of determination R Square is 0.585. This shows that the marketing mix can explain 58% of the purchase decision, and the remaining 41.5% is explained by other factors not examined, such as cultural, social, personal, and psychological factors.

Testing the hypothesis using the F test at a value of $\alpha = 0.05$ obtained the result that Fcount is greater than F-table ($2.603 > 2.47$), so it can be concluded that H_0 is rejected and H_a is accepted, which means that with a 95% confidence level, there is a positive and significant influence simultaneous marketing mix on cosmetic purchasing decisions. Testing the hypothesis using the t-test on the independent variables of product, price, place or location, and promotion on purchasing decisions as follows:

Effect of the product (X1) on purchasing decisions (Y)

The t-count value for the product variable (X1) is 2.343, and the t-table value for $\alpha = 0.05$ with degrees of freedom $100-4-1=95$ of 1.661 means $t\text{-count} > t\text{-table}$ ($2.343 > 1.661$). Then H_0 is rejected, and H_a is accepted, meaning that the product (X1) has a significant positive impact on purchasing decisions (Y).

The effect of price (X2) on purchasing decisions (Y)

The t-count value for the price variable (X2) is 1.689, and the t-table value for $\alpha = 0.05$ with degrees of freedom $100-4-1=95$ of 1.661 means $t\text{-count} > t\text{-table}$ ($1.689 > 1.661$). Then H_0 is rejected, and H_a is accepted, meaning that price (X2) has a significant positive impact on purchasing decisions (Y).

Effect of location or place (X3) on purchasing decisions (Y)

The t-count value for the place or location variable (X3) is 2.105, and the t-table value for $\alpha = 0.05$ with degrees of freedom $100-4-1=95$ of 1.661 means $t\text{-count} > t\text{-table}$ ($2.105 > 1.661$). Then H_0 is rejected, and H_a is accepted, meaning that the place or location (X3) has a significant positive impact on purchasing decisions (Y).

The effect of promotion (X4) on purchasing decisions (Y)

The t-count value of the promotion variable (X4) is 1.998, and the t-table value for $\alpha = 0.05$ with degrees of freedom $100-4-1=95$ of 1.661 means $t\text{-count} > t\text{-table}$ ($1.998 > 1.661$). Then H_0 is rejected, and H_a is accepted, meaning that promotion (X4) has a significant positive impact on purchasing decisions (Y).

Based on the results of consumer assessments regarding the effect of the cosmetics marketing mix on purchasing decisions, the following recapitulation can be seen in the following table.

Table 4: Recapitulation of Test Results on Partial Regression Coefficients

No	Independent Variables	t _{tabel}	t _{hitung}	Keterangan
1	Product (X ₁)	1,661	2,343	Has positive and significant impact
2	Price (X ₂)	1,661	1,689	Has positive and significant impact
3	Place or location (X ₃)	1,661	2,105	Has positive and significant impact
4	Promotion (X ₄)	1,661	1,998	Has positive and significant impact

Based on the table above, it can be seen that the results of the partial regression coefficient test between the marketing mix variables (product, price, place or location, and promotion) each influence the purchasing decision. The biggest variable that influences purchasing decisions is the product (X₁).

CONCLUSION AND IMPLICATIONS

Based on consumer responses to marketing mix variables and purchasing decision variables, it can be concluded that all marketing mix factors and purchasing decisions are considered good by consumers. The marketing mix, which consists of product, price, place or location, and cosmetic promotion, simultaneously and partially has a positive and significant effect on purchasing decisions.

It is recommended that cosmetic product packaging should be made even more attractive by using packaging materials, bright and simple colors. Attempts are also made to make the price offered more affordable by making several product size variants to make it more affordable. The availability of places to sell products should be intensive, meaning that the number of outlets should be increased by adding to traditional markets so that they can reach all groups. Strengthen the dissemination of information by utilizing the diversity of media as sources of information. Further research is also needed on other factors that can influence purchasing decisions, such as cultural, social, personal, and work-psychological factors.

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